

Estimation of Pastureland Biomass in the Steppe and Gobi Regions of Mongolia Using Remote Sensing

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doi: 10.5281/zenodo.20396302

Abstract: The aim of this study is to evaluate the performance of random forest (RF) and support vector machine (SVM) models for estimating pastureland biomass in the steppe and Gobi regions of Mongolia using remote sensing (RS)-based spectral variables. Correlation analysis identified several vegetation indices, such as SR, ARVI, NDVI, VARI, and GNDVI as strong predictors of biomass, owing to their sensitivity to vegetation greenness and chlorophyll content. Additional indices, including SAVI, NDWI, NDMI, MSAVI, and EVI, also showed moderate to strong relationships, highlighting the importance of soil background and vegetation moisture in semi-arid environments. In contrast, NDWIM and NDBI exhibited negative correlations, reflecting their association with non-vegetated or low-productivity areas. The results demonstrated that the RF algorithm substantially outperformed SVM, achieving higher accuracy and lower error, while SVM showed comparatively weaker performance. Overall, the findings indicate that integrating RS data with machine learning techniques, particularly RF, provides a reliable and effective approach for estimating and mapping pasture biomass across Mongolia's diverse landscapes.

Keywords: Central Asia; Gobi; steppe; biomass; machine learning.

1 Introduction

Vegetation biomass, representing the total mass of plant material, is a key ecological indicator widely used in many environmental studies (Portela et al. 2020). Strongly linked to aboveground biomass (AGB), it plays a crucial role in the global carbon cycle and contributes substantially to the regulation of terrestrial carbon sinks (Lin et al. 2023). Nonetheless, accurately estimating biomass remains challenging in heterogeneous landscapes and under varying environmental conditions, requiring robust and scalable measurement approaches (Kumar et al. 2015, Santoro and Cartus 2019). Traditional ground-based techniques require considerable manual effort and are typically limited to small spatial extents (Chen et al. 2021), highlighting the need for alternative approaches.

Over the past decade, RS has become an increasingly effective approach for estimating and mapping various forms of biomass. Advances in RS technologies have enabled rapid assessment and continuous monitoring of biomass dynamics across different spatial and temporal scales (Lourenco 2021). Among the available RS data

sources, optical imagery is particularly valuable because of its wide availability, high temporal coverage, and operational flexibility. Using optical datasets, numerous biomass estimation methods have been developed, including advanced statistical and machine learning approaches (Amarsaikhan et al. 2023). These methods are often integrated with spectral indices and ancillary environmental variables to improve model sensitivity and enhance the predictive accuracy of aboveground biomass (AGB) estimation (Zhou et al. 2021).

In Mongolia, environmental monitoring requires timely and reliable assessment of pasture biomass to support sustainable rangeland management practices (Otgonbayar et al. 2019, Ulziibaatar and Matsui 2021). This demand is particularly important because the country's vast grassland ecosystems are highly vulnerable to climate variability, overgrazing, and land-use change (Li et al. 2024). Although high-resolution satellite imagery can provide detailed spatial information and potentially improve biomass estimation accuracy, its application often requires complex, labor-intensive, and time-consuming preprocessing and analytical procedures (Thenkabil et al. 2012).

Moreover, the large data volumes associated with high-resolution imagery can limit its operational use for nationwide or long-term monitoring (Pettoirelli et al. 2014). In contrast, moderate-resolution data enable faster data processing and more operational large-scale biomass estimation, despite offering lower spatial detail (Eisfelder et al. 2012). Their wide spatial coverage, frequent temporal revisit, and easier accessibility make them particularly suitable for national-scale pasture monitoring applications in Mongolia.

This study evaluates the ability of RF and SVM models to rapidly estimate pasture biomass in Mongolia's steppe and Gobi regions using spectral indices derived from the MOD13A1 product and compares their performance to identify the most reliable approach.

2 Materials and methods

The Mongolian steppe forms a major part of the Eurasian steppe belt, one of the largest continuous grassland ecosystems in the world. Extending across the central and eastern regions of Mongolia, this ecosystem is characterized by vast open landscapes dominated by drought-tolerant grass species such as *Stipa*, *Leymus*, and *Cleistogenes*. These grasslands play a vital role in

sustaining traditional pastoral livestock systems, which remain a cornerstone of Mongolia's socio-economic structure, while also supporting significant levels of biodiversity (Munkhzul et al. 2021).

South of the steppe lies the Gobi region, one of the world's largest cold desert environments, extending across southern Mongolia. The Gobi landscape consists of gravel plains, rocky plateaus, dry valleys, and scattered sand dunes. Due to extremely low and highly variable precipitation, vegetation cover is sparse, and dominant plant communities consist of species well adapted to arid and semi-arid conditions, reflecting strong environmental limitations on primary productivity (Batsaikhan et al. 2014). Figure 1 shows a map that illustrates the steppe and Gobi regions in Mongolia.

Figure 1. Steppe and Gobi regions of Mongolia (1). Number (2) indicates forested and other land-cover areas.

Field data were obtained from the Information and Research Institute of Meteorology, Hydrology and Environment under the Ministry of Environment and Tourism of Mongolia, which conducts nationwide rangeland biomass monitoring. In the study area, biomass measurements from 158 plots collected in the middle of August 2021 were used. Samples were sealed in plastic bags, transported to meteorological stations, and analyzed in the laboratory. There, biomass was oven-dried, and dry weight was calculated, normalized by plot area, and expressed in kilograms per hectare (kg/ha) (SDC and GGP 2015).

Figure 2. Locations of the sampling sites.

For biomass prediction, twelve spectral indices Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index (ARVI), Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI), Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (GNDVI), Modified Soil-

Adjusted Vegetation Index (MSAVI), Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI), Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI), Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), Normalized Difference Water Index Modified (NDWIM), Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI), Simple Ratio (SR), and Visible Atmospherically Resistant Index (VARI) derived from MOD13A1 data (Jargaldalai et al. 2022) acquired in August 2021 were used. Detailed descriptions about these indices are given in Amarsaikhan et al. (2023). Locations of the selected 158 sampling sites are shown in Figure 2.

In the final classification, we applied and compared RF and SVM methods to estimate vegetation biomass in the steppe and Gobi regions of Mongolia.

The RF classifier is a widely used ensemble learning technique that constructs multiple decision trees by randomly sampling subsets of both training data and predictor variables. Each tree is organized hierarchically, with nodes split according to selected features and defined criteria (Amarsaikhan et al. 2024). RF has become a standard approach in remote sensing and geospatial applications due to its robust classification accuracy and reliability (Belgiu and Drăguț 2016). A major advantage of this method lies in its ability to efficiently handle large, complex datasets while maintaining resilience against noise and outliers (Rodriguez-Galiano et al. 2012).

The SVM is regarded as one of the most robust prediction techniques within the statistical learning framework (Pal and Mather 2005). At its core, the method constructs a set of hyperplanes in a high-dimensional feature space to separate input data into distinct classes. The optimal separation is achieved by identifying the hyperplane that maximizes the margin, the distance between the hyperplane and the nearest training samples from each class. In general, a larger margin corresponds to a lower classification error, thereby enhancing the generalization ability of the model (Hastie et al. 2009). Beyond its theoretical sophistication, SVM has been widely applied in RS and geospatial sciences due to its capacity to handle complex and non-linear relationships (Maxwell et al. 2018).

3 Results

Mongolia is characterized by a wide range of natural and geographical zones, each supporting distinct vegetation communities and associated biomass levels. This natural diversity is reflected in the field-measured AGB data collected across the country.

As part of the analytical approach, this study aimed to identify which spectral features derived from RS data were most strongly associated with ground-measured biomass. To quantify these relationships, Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated and summarized in a correlation matrix (Figure 3).

The results revealed that several vegetation indices exhibited strong linear relationships with biomass. Notably, indices such as SR, ARVI, NDVI, and VARI showed correlation coefficients (r) ranging from 0.63 to 0.70, indicating strong positive relationships with AGB.

Another group of indices, including SAVI, NDWI, NDMI, MSAVI, GNDVI, and EVI, also demonstrated moderate to strong associations, with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.57 to 0.61. These indices appear to be effective in capturing variations in AGB among the evaluated RS variables. In contrast, two indices exhibited negative correlations with biomass. In particular, NDWIM showed a strong negative correlation with AGB ($r = -0.61$), while NDBI also demonstrated a moderately strong negative relationship ($r = -0.57$).

Figure 3. Correlation coefficients matrix for the selected variables and biomass.

After training and validation, the models were used to generate spatial distribution maps of biomass across the study area (Figure 4). To quantitatively evaluate and compare model performance, two widely used statistical metrics—the coefficient of determination (R^2) and root mean square error (RMSE)—were employed, following previous studies (Tsolmon et al. 2022).

The results indicated that the RF model achieved higher predictive accuracy, with an R^2 of 0.894 and RMSE of 0.85 kg/ha. In contrast, the SVM model showed lower performance, with an R^2 of 0.522 and RMSE of 1.33 kg/ha.

Furthermore, linear regression analyses were conducted to examine the relationship between observed and predicted biomass values. The corresponding scatterplots are presented in Figure 5. As shown, the RF model exhibited a strong agreement between observed and predicted values ($R^2 = 0.894$), whereas the SVM model demonstrated weaker performance ($R^2 = 0.522$).

Figure 4. The results of the classifications (biomass maps) using: (a) RF, and (b) SVM.

4 Discussion

Figure 5. Accuracy analysis: (a) RF, and (b) SVM

The results of this study highlight the strong influence of Mongolia’s diverse natural and geographical conditions on the spatial variability of the AGB. This observation aligns closely with findings from prior investigations in arid and semi-arid ecosystems, where biomass dynamics are strongly governed by climatic gradients, soil characteristics, and topographic conditions (Kang et al. 2013, Wang et al. 2019). Such environments are particularly sensitive to fluctuations in precipitation, temperature, and soil fertility, making them ideal case studies for understanding vegetation responses to environmental stressors (Wang et al. 2022).

The correlation analysis provided important insights into the relationships between spectral indices and field-measured biomass. Several vegetation indices, including SR, ARVI, NDVI, VARI, and GNDVI, demonstrated strong positive correlations ($r = 0.63\text{--}0.70$) with AGB. These indices are primarily sensitive to vegetation greenness, chlorophyll content, and canopy structure, which are directly linked to biomass accumulation.

Another group of indices, such as SAVI, NDWI, NDMI, MSAVI, and EVI, also showed moderate to strong correlations ($r = 0.57\text{--}0.61$). These indices incorporate adjustments for soil background effects (e.g., SAVI, MSAVI) and vegetation moisture content (e.g., NDWI, NDMI), which are especially relevant in Mongolia's dryland environments. The relatively strong performance of these indices suggests that both soil reflectance and plant water content play significant roles in determining biomass variability in semi-arid regions.

In contrast, the negative correlations observed for NDWIM ($r = -0.61$) and NDBI ($r = -0.57$) provide additional ecological insight. NDWIM is associated with water-related spectral responses, and its inverse relationship with biomass may indicate that areas with higher surface moisture or non-vegetated water signals correspond to lower vegetation density in this context. Similarly, NDBI, which is typically used to identify built-up or bare land areas, shows a negative relationship with biomass, as expected.

The machine learning results further demonstrate the effectiveness of integrating RS data with advanced modeling techniques. The RF model significantly outperformed the SVM, achieving a high coefficient of determination and low RMSE. This superior performance can be attributed to the inherent advantages of RF, including its ability to model complex non-linear relationships, handle high-dimensional data, and reduce overfitting through ensemble learning.

On the other hand, the relatively lower performance of the SVM model suggests that it was less effective in capturing the complex relationships between spectral features and biomass in this study. This may be due to the sensitivity of SVM to parameter selection and its limited ability to generalize when the underlying relationships are highly non-linear and influenced by heterogeneous environmental conditions.

5 Conclusions

This study evaluated the performance of RF and SVM models for estimating aboveground biomass (AGB) in the pasturelands of Mongolia's steppe and Gobi regions using spectral variables extracted from RS data. The correlation analysis revealed that vegetation indices such as NDVI, VARI, ARVI, and SR are reliable indicators of biomass because of their strong sensitivity to vegetation greenness and chlorophyll content. In addition, indices incorporating soil background and vegetation moisture information, including SAVI, MSAVI, NDWI, GNDVI, NDMI, and EVI, also showed strong applicability under semi-arid environmental conditions. In contrast, indices such as

NDWIM and NDBI exhibited negative relationships with biomass, indicating their association with non-vegetated or sparsely vegetated surfaces. Regarding model performance, the RF algorithm substantially outperformed the SVM, achieving higher accuracy ($R^2 = 0.894$) and lower prediction error (RMSE = 0.85 kg/ha). On the other hand, the comparatively lower performance of the SVM model suggests limitations in representing the spatial heterogeneity of biomass under varying environmental conditions. Overall, the study demonstrates that combining RS data with machine learning techniques, especially the RF algorithm, provides a robust and efficient approach for estimating pasture biomass in Mongolia's steppe and Gobi regions.

6 References

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